

The TRIZ Method of the Multistory Layout and its Application in the Field of Fine Arts

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Abstract: The author's research is focused on the field of fine arts research through the prism of structural analysis of TRIZ methods. This article is devoted to studying the possibilities of using the multi-story (multi-tier) layout method in an image. The main options for using this method are identified, an interpretation of images is proposed, and an analysis of the functions of shaping methods, their features, specificity, and resource capabilities is suggested. This method is organically integrated into modern

visual language, enriching it both semantically and plastically. The article also briefly describes the process of teaching material regarding this method as part of the Visual Language Grammar course.

Keywords: modern visual language, TRIZ methods, multi-story layout, image interpretation, image semantics.

Rezumat: Articolul se concentrează pe domeniul cercetării artelor plastice prin prisma analizei structurale a metodelor TRIZ, fiind dedicat studierii posibilităților de utilizare a metodei de layout multi-nivel într-o imagine. Sunt identificate principalele opțiuni de utilizare a acestei metode, se propune o interpretare a imaginilor; se propune o analiză a funcțiilor metodelor de modelare, se prezintă caracteristicile acestora, specificul și posibilitățile de obținere a resurselor. Această metodă este integrată organic în limbajul vizual modern, îmbogățindu-l atât din punct de vedere semantic, cât și plastic. De asemenea, articolul descrie pe scurt procesul de predare a materialului legat de aceste metode în cadrul cursului Gramatica limbajului vizual.

Cuvinte-cheie: limbaj vizual modern, metoda TRIZ, layout multi-nivel, interpretare a imaginii, semantică a imaginii.

In the modern world, a "visual turn" that has disrupted "the established relationship between the visual and the verbal in public life in favor of the visual" has happened [10, p. 39]. The current situation requires a reconsideration of the attitude towards the creative process, highlights the need to study the complex and multidimensional modern visual language as a whole, isolates and analyzes its components, expands knowledge about various cultural and historical contexts of the visual, requires a conscious selection of new artistic images and methods of their implementation, and necessitates the adoption of current methods for increasing artistic expressiveness.

The purpose of this article is to study the capabilities of one of the TRIZ methods, the Multi-Story Layout Method, when applied in the field of fine arts. Genrikh Altshuller gave the following description of this TRIZ method: "Use a multi-story layout of objects instead of a single-story one" [2, p. 52].

A synonym for a composition with a multi-story layout is a tiered composition. Below, there are examples of this layout method application in the art of ancient Egypt (Figure 1), Mesopotamia (Figure 2), ancient India (Figure 3), and ancient China (Figure 4). Examples of this method are also found in the art of Ancient Greece, Byzantium, in the Renaissance and Baroque periods, and in the works of 20th century artists, who willingly used this method. In a word, compositions of this kind have been used from ancient times to the present.

Figure 1. Examples of the application of the multi-story layout method in the art of ancient Egypt. a) Plate (palette) of Pharaoh Narmer. Approx. 3000 BC; b) Book of Amduat, Cyperus papyrus, detail of Thebes, between 1076 and 722 BC; c) Obelisk of Queen Hatshepsut in the Temple of Amun at Karnak, XVIII Dynasty, 1457 BC.

Figure 2. Examples of the application of the multi-story layout method in the art of Mesopotamia. Standard of War and Peace. Mid-3rd millennium BC: a) War, b) Peace.

Figure 3. Examples of the application of the multi-story layout method in the art of ancient India. a) Northern gate of the stupa in Sanchi. 1st century BC; b) Mahabodhi Temple in Bodh Gaya. Approx. 5th century AD; c) Entrance to Chaitya No. 19 at Ajanta. 6th century AD

Figure 4. Examples of the application of the multi-story layout method in the art of ancient China. a) Hu type vessel. Bronze. Zhangguo period. 5th-3rd centuries BC; b) Reception at the palace. Relief from the tomb of Wu Liang-Tsing. Shandong Province. Han period. 147 AD; c) Battle on the bridge. Relief from the tomb of Wu Liang-Tsing. Shandong Province. Han period. 147 AD.

The study of numerous visual materials using this method made it possible to identify the following functional possibilities for the use of the multi-story layout method.

Multi-tiered composition is used in various contexts. The first group includes the use of this method for structuring the visual space. In this case, each tier is assigned a special meaning and characteristic features. Development can go from lower levels to higher ones, from closer plans to more distant ones. If the composition describes the development of the plot in time, then, as a rule, earlier events are located lower and later events are higher. In some images, objects may be located at different levels that are not related by one common feature. The second group includes compositions in which a multi-tiered structure is used to create metaphorical images – for example, in order to reflect the complexity, instability, fragility, balance, or weightlessness of an object. In the third group, this method is used exclusively as a plastic tool, intended to create interesting formal solutions. The common feature of all groups is the ability to arrange a large number of objects without chaos and disorder.

Let us consider the options and functionality of using the Multi-Story Layout Method in more detail. One of the most important functions of using a multi-story layout is **to show a multi-tier arrangement of something**. Each level can represent a specific aspect of a theme or idea that the artist wishes to express, and the interaction between levels can enhance the semantic depth of the work and create a multi-layered structure of the work. As the semeiologist B. Uspensky notes, in art “complex compositional structures are possible, when different structures of the same work are identified at different levels of analysis.” [14, p.134] Thus, since ancient times, artists have used such a composition **to reflect ideas about the structure of the world** (Figure 5). This makes reference to the ancient traditions of different peoples, according to which the world is divided into three main parts: underground, earth and heaven. The historian V. Evsyukov notes that: “the idea of the universe as a grandiose multi-story building at a certain stage in the development of religion and mythology was inherent in an extremely wide range of peoples almost all over the world . . . Such a universe can be figuratively compared to a multi-storied building, the upper floors of which correspond to the heavens inhabited by gods, the middle floors to the earth, the abode of people, and the lower ones were given over to all kinds of demons and evil spirits...

Figure 5. Examples of using the multi-story layout method to reflect the multi-tier structure of the world: a) Mount Meru and the Jambudvipa disk. Buddhist universe; b) Seven heavenly spheres, according to Muslim ideas; c) Dante's Purgatory; d) Drawing of the upper world of the Dayaks of the Ngaju tribe.

Traces of such ideas are found in Ancient Greece, the Middle East, India, China, Central Asia, as well as in the religious traditions of other regions” [5, pp. 1-41]. In fact, this is how the model of the Universe was imagined by the ancients, as I. Ibragimov explains: ”such a system, which has several levels, imagined by man around the earth’s firmament, can be characterized as a coordinate system of the earth in human religious ideas” [6, p. 7]. The use of a pyramidal multi-level structure to reflect the structure of the world can symbolize the levels in their development from the lower plan of multiplicity and fragmentation to the higher plan of unity.

Not only the world, but also other studied phenomena can be presented multi-tiered; for example, sometimes such a composition is used as **an indication of the multi-story nature of the human psyche**, the complexity of its structure, the presence of various aspects of human consciousness and the unconscious. The complexity of the human inner world was understood since ancient times. Nowadays, this concept is considered in various areas of psychology and suggests that the human psyche has several levels or layers, each of which plays a role in the development of personality and behavior. As Nikolai Berdyaev wrote, “man is a microcosm and contains everything. The man is a multi-story creature as well. I always felt that multi-storiedness of mine” [4, p. 5]. Carl Gustav Jung in one of his works also compared the human psyche to a multi-story building, the foundation of which was laid in primitive times, and the number of floors was erected over subsequent eras. The person himself lives on the upper floors of a modern building and is not aware of the archaic masonry on which the entire building rests [11]. This idea is also reflected in the visual arts. Brahma, Vishnu, Shiva and other divine Hindu beings (Figure 6 a, b) are sometimes depicted with multiple heads, reflecting various aspects of their strength and abilities, including the ability to perform multiple actions. Modern artists also use a multi-tiered layout to reflect the complexity of the human psyche (Figure 6 d).

Figure 6. Application of the multi-story layout method to indicate the multi-story nature of the human psyche. a) The Hindu god Shiva with 26 heads and 52 arms. Brihadishvara Temple in Tamil Nadu, ancient India; b) Dharmapala Rahula; c) Louis Jover. *Einstein Mechanics*; d) Lorenzo Petratoni.

Very often, simultaneously with the task of showing the structure of something, the task of **reflecting the hierarchy of the depicted objects is set** (Figure 7). At the upper levels, as a rule, more important figures, scenes, and components are depicted, while at the lower levels less significant elements are located, creating a hierarchy of significance. Thus, on the relief in Luxor (Figure 7 a) the wife of the ruling pharaoh is depicted surrounded by goddesses handing over a baby to her. It is no coincidence that the pharaoh’s wife and the goddesses are on the same level; this emphasizes the equal position of the gods and the pharaoh’s family: ”This religious position was first introduced by the female pharaoh Hatshepsut (XVIII dynasty), but it is not her own theological ”invention” but only a transformation of the concept that developed in the Old Kingdom, according to which the pharaohs are the sons of the Sun” [12, p. 112]. L. Akimova, describing the scene of the birth of Pandora on the base of an ancient Greek statue, emphasizes: ”the birth of Pandora, placed in the lower tier of the statue, hinted at the creation of a woman and her dependence on men, which was confirmed by her name – ‘gifted by all’” [1, p. 208].

Figure 7. Application of the multi-story layout method to reflect the hierarchy of those depicted: a) The birth of the future pharaoh Amenhotep III; b) Icon. *The triumph of Orthodoxy. Byzantium. XIV century*; Etienne Delessert. *Children’s book cover*; d) Júlia Sarda. *Illustration*.

Another possible function of a multi-story layout is **to convey spatial relationships**. A multi-tiered composition allows the artist to create the impression of depth and spatial perspective. Different levels or “tiers” in paintings can be created by placing objects or elements in the foreground, middle, and background. This helps the viewer to feel the depth of space and enter the depicted world. This arrangement makes it possible to place a large number of objects in a compact and clear manner. This technique was widely used in Persian painting (8 a, b): the lower objects are closer, while in the upper rows the distant ones are placed without changing their size. Modern artists also use this method to reflect what is happening on different floors at the same time (Figure 8 c, d).

Figure 8. Examples of using the multi-story layout method to convey spatial relationships: a) Persian miniature. Feast in a Baghdad courtyard; b) Sultan Mohammed. Sultan Sanjar and the old woman. Miniature of the 16th-century Tabriz school by “Khamisa” Nizami. 1539-43; c) Victoria Tentler-Krylova. Illustration; d) Josan Gonzales. Illustration.

A multi-story layout can also serve to **reflect the development of a plot over time** (Figure 9). Thus, “in the ancient Greek sarcophagus of Alexander of Sidon (Figure 9 b) the strict division of the sarcophagus into three vertical zones (basement – temple – attic) builds a system of times: past (“royal hunt”), present (mourning), and future (departure)” [1, p. 326]. In this case the three-tiered image is associated with the idea of transformation. At the same time, the texts of the ancient Egyptian *Book of Amduat* (Figure 1 b) tell us, in a peculiar fantastic manner, about twelve caves of the underworld, traversed by the Sun-Ra during twelve hours of the night. In connection to the motif of passing through various stages, it is worth mentioning the symbol of a ladder, which “represents an imaginary support for spiritual, moral or cognitive ascent. It indicates the desire to restore the lost contact between humanity and divinity, between heaven and earth. In Christian iconography it consists of seven or twelve steps. In the first case, they correspond to different levels of spiritual ascent through the spheres of the planets, which the soul must cross before reaching the sphere of the fixed stars, or the seven free arts, a symbol of achievement of perfection through education, knowledge and morality, and in the second case, they correspond to the twelve apostles. The staircase symbolizes transition like initiation, with the goal of either Heaven or Hell” [3, p. 238]. As an example of the use of the multi-story layout method in order to describe the development of events over time, we must mention one of the most famous historical monuments of Rome, Trajan’s Column. Covering the trunk of the Column, a multi-tiered relief frieze reproduces about 150 episodes of the Dacian wars of emperor Trajan. (Figure 9 c).

Figure 9. Application of the multi-story layout method to develop the plot over time: a) Birth of the god Brahma; b) The sarcophagus of Alexander of Sidon. Marble. Approx. 320–310 BC; c) Trajan’s Column. Fragment. 113 AD; d) Vladimir Konashevich. Illustration.

The multi-story layout that structures the image is used not only in art, but also for illustration in scientific research. Modern people are well aware of various multi-level models – for example, the family tree, Abraham Maslow’s pyramid of needs, John Dewey’s pyramid of knowledge etc. (Figure 10). These models are intuitive to most people and allow one to clearly illustrate complex concepts. The pyramidal structure may reflect the fundamental importance of the lower layers and the top as the final stage, the culmination. In modern cultural studies, the multi-tiered structure of the world can be considered as a complex network of sociocultural, political, economic and other levels and subsystems that interact with each other and influence the lives and behavior of people.

Figure 10. Examples of the use of multi-story models in science. a) Diagram of the oldest family tree. Newcastle University; b) Diagram of Abraham Maslow’s hierarchy of human needs; c) John Dewey’s Pyramid of Knowledge.

Multi-tiered compositions can be used to convey complex symbolic ideas or metaphorical concepts, to transcribe meanings. In an article about the art of A. Tyshler (Figure 11 a, b) E. Mazova, when discussing the artist’s use of tiered compositions, points out that “the technique of combining real... and virtual spaces in a single scenic volume... contributed to the scenographic embodiment of the principle of the “pregnant world” – the unification of multiple structures in a single image... Indicated within the framework of this study, as a tiered organization of composition elements, this technique provides the artist with extensive opportunities for a highly theatrical transcription of a dramatic text... As A. Tyshler wrote, explaining his compositional ideas: “You can make thousands, millions of spatial resolutions on the canvas” [9, pp. 135-136].

Figure 11. Application of the multi-story layout method for the development of the plot over time a) A. Tyshler. Demonstration of disabled people. 1925; b) A. Tyshler. Fragment from the Lyrical Cycle. 1928; c) Ester Garcia. Illustration; D) Vera Pavlova. Illustration.

A multi-tiered composition is well suited for **creating metaphors of instability, fragility and balance** (Figure 12) Attention is drawn to the fact that, due to the obvious instability of the multi-story layout, the ancient people tried to "strengthen and secure the tiered structure". As I. Ibragimov writes, "in order for the system to become stable, various elements are invented with the help of which the earthly level is supposedly maintained (elephants, turtles, whales, etc.). The system "sticks around" from all sides and most of all from the bottom side, because the "bottom", as a foundation, should have greater stability in the ideas of ancient man" [6, p.10]. To enhance the instability of a multi-tiered structure, a composition in the shape of a triangle resting on one vertex is sometimes used.

Figure 12. Using the multi-story layout method to create a metaphor for fragility and balance. a) Weedfrog. Illustration. Earth on Three Elephants, 1925; b) A. Tyshler. Fragment from the Lyrical Cycle. 1928; c) Sonya Wimmer. Book cover; d) Thomas Martin. Still life.

Often, a multi-story layout is used to create unreal, mysterious spaces generated by the author's imagination (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Using the multi-story layout method to create unreal, mysterious spaces. a) Auseklis Bauškenieks; b) João Vaz de Carvalho; c) Pavel Tatarnikov; d) Ofra Amit; e) Sugimoto Sanae.

The use of a multi-story layout method can be used exclusively **as a formal solution** (Figure 14) to create a bright plastic image. The vertical arrangement of objects does not always have a sacred, symbolic, metaphorical meaning.

Figure 14. Using the multi-story layout method to create an interesting still life composition. Authors: a) Daria Pri-machek; b) Olga Jordan; c) Aad Hofman; d) Irena Aizen; E) Kenne Gregoire Stacking.

Based on the research described in [7] and [8], the author has developed a training course program for *Grammar of Visual Language* using TRIZ methods for graphic design students from the Ion Creangă State Pedagogical University of Chişinău, Faculty of Fine Arts and Design, Department of Art History, Graphics, and Teaching Methodology. This course involves theoretical classes, seminars, and practical classes. The logic of the course consistently develops the components of students' interpretative and artistic skills and leads them to master the mechanism of generating meaning through works of fine art.

During the introductory stage (Challenge Stage) the students are presented with a series of images based on a new topic for interpretation. Here are examples of questions on the multi-story layout method suggested to students at this stage:

- What unites all these images?
- Why did the author use a multi-tiered layout?
- What are your associations and feelings when looking at these images?
- Is the author able to convey a message using this method?
- What additional opportunities appear when using this method?
- How does the use of this method affect the plasticity of the image?

Students express their points of view on the topic, giving reasons and examples, and exchange ideas and impressions. Collective generation of ideas is encouraged. This methodological approach is based on the Reading and Writing for Critical Thinking techniques, developed in the USA in the late 1980s [13]. The challenge stage is used to activate students' artistic thinking and their emotional involvement in the research process. This task contributes to the development of speech skills, the ability to reflect, the ability to justify one's point of view, look for

alternatives, and show an informed and open mind.

Further along the program the students are provided with theoretical information about this specific TRIZ method. The presentation provides a historical overview of images using this method from ancient times to the present day, as well as ideas, theories, interpretations, and conceptual approaches of art historians, philosophers, cultural experts, psychologists, artists, and other researchers, which allow us to link the visual range of works to concepts of the modern world. The theoretical material contributes to the transition from a superficial naturalistic perception of works of art to the disclosure of deep hidden meanings and significances. When presenting theoretical material the teacher will sometimes ask questions in order to maintain the students' attention. To summarize, a discussion is organized in the final part of the lesson. Students share their impressions, focus on the new things they have learnt, what touched them, surprised them, and interested them. Each participant expresses their thoughts and impressions about the possibilities of this method. Classroom sessions also regularly feature the work of various artists for one's own interpretation.

Completing practical assignments is a necessary and integral part of the course, helping to improve the quality of learning and activity levels, as well as students' independence in solving creative problems. Extracurricular independent work is organized using Google Classroom, a web service where educational materials and assignments are posted and students receive grades, feedback, and comments. Google Classroom provides flexibility and convenience in organizing the educational process. In order to systematize, consolidate and comprehend the theoretical material covered, and correlate it with existing knowledge, the students need to select images from various authors for each of the TRIZ methods with their own brief interpretation.

Figure 15. Students' sketches (Ion Creangă State Pedagogical University of Chişinău, Department of Art History, Graphics and Teaching Methodology) using the Multi-Story Layout Method: a – Vladimir Lyniuk, b – Lilia Cretu, c – Alexandra Shaposhnikova, e) Timur Fedorenko.

To develop creative imagination and conscious application of the TRIZ multi-story layout method, the task is given to create an artistic image and develop a sketch of the image using this method. Below are examples of sketches by first-year students using the multi-story layout method (Figure 15). In order to activate reflection and conceptual thinking, it is necessary to accompany the sketch with textual analysis explaining for what purposes this method was used. If mistakes were made during the practical task, it is recommended to review the training materials and then make the necessary corrections.

Once students have gained an understanding of the various TRIZ methods, they are tasked with creating an artistic image using several TRIZ methods simultaneously.

In summarizing the results of this part of the study, we can mention that the use of the multi-story layout method by artists has deep historical roots and represents a multifaceted phenomenon of a system of visual techniques developed by mankind. Different elements at different levels can evoke different associations and emotional reactions, which makes the work more multifaceted and open to interpretation. This method is organically integrated into modern visual discourse, enriching it with various semantic loads, and contributes to the formation of visual messages, which in turn contributes to the development of compositional and figurative thinking of the future artist.

An analysis of the results obtained after taking the course *Visual Language Grammar* through the prism of TRIZ methods generally demonstrated that the students:

- were able to develop an active position during the study of units of modern visual language;
- have shown an increased interest in the interpretation of images and a desire to independently expand and deepen knowledge in the field of art and culture;
- increased the level of reflection and sensitivity to works of art, had a desire to comprehend the meanings, feelings, ideas, and logic of formal composition embedded in the image;
- developed artistic taste, showed a desire to create, as well as originality and novelty in emerging artistic associations;
- confirmed that this course can become a starting point for a full-scale study of modern complex and multidimensional visual culture.

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